

Event Schema as a Semantic Component of Events

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Abstract

Relationship between the main arguments of a Predicator Verb is explained variously by summoning one or more of a set of syntactic and semantic properties related to the Verb such as adicity, transitivity, agentivity and event schema. This paper prioritizes event schema, as conceptualized in Cognitive linguistics, for configuring the relationship between the main arguments and their thematic roles, known as Participant roles, as a more appropriate interpretation of Interlingual Asymmetry (IA), such as those occurring in the grammatical case of the Verb's main arguments, between English and Tamil. Further, it projects the event schema as a non-temporal functional semantic component of events.

Keywords: *participant roles, thematic roles, semantic component, event schema, cognitive linguistics, interlingual asymmetry.*

1. Introduction

In this paper, a semantic component concerned with a non-temporal dimension of Events that is considered significant for studying translation shift/IA between CE and CT in the context of Event mediation from the former to the latter is taken up for discussion. Event Schema refers to the way an event is construed or conceptualized with respect to the participant roles of the Event in a message and the inter-relation between those roles. This is considered to be a universal phenomenon (Verspoor, Dirven and Radden, 2004), entailing its occurrence in CT as well. The Event Schema is realized in the form of certain sentence patterns and predicate constructions that are asymmetric across languages. It is this potential for equivalence in meaning but asymmetry in form that is of interest to the wider research concerning translation shifts, of which this paper is a part.

2. Aims and Objectives

The purpose of an analytical description of event schema presented in this paper is to serve as a groundwork for studying Interlingual Asymmetry (IA) between English and Tamil while mediating event meanings from the former to the latter in translation. To this end, the event schema is shown as a semantic component that could be taken as the invariant or the trigger that leads to formal variations between the two languages, especially the asymmetry in

grammatical case of Subject, Object and Complement NPs around the predicator Verb in a clause.

3. Methodology

The paper sets out to distinguish the different denotation of the term Event Schema in vogue in the event-centric language processing trends in contemporary linguistics, emphasizing its perspective within Cognitive linguistics, a family of approaches towards descriptive linguistics from a functional and cognitive viewpoint (Radden and Dirven, 2007), some of whose leading proponents and their works are Haiman (1985), Langacker (1987, 1991), Wierzbicka (1988), Givón (1993), Goldberg (1995), Fauconnier (1997), Lakoff (1993), Coulson (2000) and Hampe (2004), among others.

It traces the origin of this concept from the term ‘schema’, its evolution through the concepts of Image Schema and Conceptual Metaphor in Cognitive linguistics leading to the category of Event Schema. In this process, its distinction from a related but discrete sense as used in compositionality of Verb meaning (see, for example, Rappapov and Levin, 1998; Levin, 1999; Grimshaw, 2005) is clarified.

This sifting out of the identity of event schema within Cognitive linguistics is followed by its definition as a semantic component of events that pertains to events as a class and of non-temporal dimension, picking out its main features for a brief explanation. The paper then proceeds to present the two available schemes of classification or grouping for the event schema, prioritizing the one that offers a more elaborate approach, a taxonomy.

By way of elucidation of the types and subtypes of this taxonomy, illustrative examples are listed in both English and Tamil, along with a brief introduction, features and different communicative functions of the categories, as well as a mapping of the categories between the two classifications.

4. Literature Review

The concept of Event schema appears in the context of developing semantic models of events in two prominent approaches, both of which are event-centric. One is Event Semantics (ES) and the other is Cognitive Linguistics.

Gardenfors (2023) mentions three approaches in describing events: the metaphysical approach that analyzes and explains ontology of events (Davidson, 1967; Kim, 1976; Casati and Varzi, 2008, among others); the cognitive models, subdivided into two, namely mental representation of events and construals (for example, Langacker, 1987; Givón, 2001; Croft, 2012) and, the linguistic expressions explaining event construals (Levin, 2009, 2015). It is the last two that factors Event Schema into the analysis of event meanings.

4.1 Event Schema in Event Semantics

Event Semantics (ES) says that clauses in natural languages are descriptions of events (Williams, 2021). Clauses, the key units representing the messages or propositions that make up a text, are viewed as woven around events. In analyzing the semantics of an event, and therefore the Verb which represents it, a bipartite structure has been proposed (Levin, 2009). One is known as **semantic structure** and the other is **semantic content** (Grimshaw, 2005). The former meaning is a shared part by the members of a Verb class, i.e. it recurs across a set of Verbs, while the latter is idiosyncratic, unique to each member in the class (Levin, 2009, 2015).

The **semantic content** is called Root. The **semantic structure** is otherwise known by the term Event Schema, which is described as composed of primitive predicates (Carter, 1978; Wilks, 1987), given in terms of ACT, CAUSE and BECOME as follows:

- a. ACTIVITY: 'x acts in a manner w'
- b. DIRECTED MOTION: 'x moves in a manner w along a path y'
- c. CAUSED CHANGE OF STATE: '[x acts on y in manner w] cause [y become z]' (Levin, 2009)

Event Schemas are divided into simple and complex types. The former consists of only one subevent, while the latter comprises two subevents, namely the **causing subevent** and the **result subevent** (Morgan, 1969; McCawley, 1971; Dowty, 1979; Rappaport and Levin, 1998; Levin, 1999).

The meaning of an event is constructed by combining its Root with the Event Schema of the class to which it belongs, and formally realized using one of the morphosyntactic frames given below suitable for that class.

- a. Intransitive construction: NP V
- b. Intransitive construction with PP: NP V PP
- c. Transitive construction: NP V NP

4.2 Schema, Image Schema and Conceptual Metaphor

The concept and use of Event Schema in Cognitive Linguistics is relatively recent. It derives from related concepts such as schema, image schema and conceptual metaphor in psychology, cognitive science and linguistics.

The origin of the word '**Schema**' is the Greek term *schēmat* or *schēma*, which means "figure" (Oakley, 2007; John and Idris, 2022) and known to have been used in philosophy. Later the idea was picked up by gestalt psychologists and first used in psychology by Piaget (1926). It deals with organization of information and knowledge into categories that enables developing a framework for future understanding (DiMaggio, 1997; Boutyline and Soter, 2021).

Earlier, in philosophy, Immanuel Kant used the term in the context of cognitive representation. His notion of schema related percepts to concepts (Johnson, 1987). For him,

schemas are structures of imagination, which is the mental faculty that processes various modes of representation into concepts (Oakley, 2007). He explained it as follows.

“Indeed, it is schemas, not images of objects, which underlie our pure sensible concepts...The concept ‘dog’ signifies a rule according to which my imagination can delineate the figure of a four-footed animal in a general manner” (Kant [1781] in Sinha, 2007, p.1270).

It is this description that relates to other concepts leading up to Event Schema that is more relevant to this study.

Image Schema are condensed redescriptions of our perceptual experiences that enable the mapping of spatial structure onto conceptual structure (Oakley, 2007). It refers to the pattern captured from the perceptions and actions we experience giving it a coherent structure in the mind (Johnson, 1987).

For Lakoff (1987), they are relatively simple mental image structures formed from our everyday bodily experiences vis-à-vis its environment that are repeated. Some of the image schemas that he listed are containers, paths, links, forces, balance, which occur in various orientations and relations such as up-down, front-back, part-whole, center-periphery and so on.

“Human beings generate mental images all the time. In Cognitive Linguistics, the term image implicates perception in all acts of conceptualization. Concepts (even abstract concepts) develop from representations of a perceptual conglomeration of visual, auditory, haptic, motoric, olfactory, and gustatory experiences. Images are always analogue representations of specific things or activities. (Oakley, 2007, p.216)”

Conceptual Metaphor refers to comprehending an idea by comparing and correlating it with another. The domain of experience containing the idea that helps in understanding is known as the **source domain**, while the domain of experience of the interpreted idea is the **target domain**. For example, in the proposition *Life is a journey*, ‘life’ is understood in terms of ‘journey’, hence the former belongs to the target domain and the latter to the source domain. The linkages of corresponding points in the source and target domains that help in this understanding are known as **mappings** (Kövecses, 2010).

Conceptual Metaphors were developed in the works of George Lakoff and Mark Johnson, two of the pioneering Cognitive linguists (Lakoff and Johnson, 1980; Lakoff and Turner, 1989; Lakoff, 1993). Three overlapping categories of conceptual metaphors were delineated by Lakoff and Johnson (1980), namely Orientational Metaphor, Ontological Metaphor and Structural Metaphor. Some examples of conceptual metaphors and their actual expressions in language are given in the table below.

Table-1: Conceptual Metaphors with Expressions (Radden and Dirven, 2007)

Conceptual metaphor	Metaphorical expression
Time is money	I've invested a lot of time in her.
Love is madness	I am crazy about her.
Beliefs are possessions	He clings to his beliefs.
More is up	Oil prices are rising again.
Connection is contact	Please hold on!
The future is in front	I look forward to seeing you.

Table-2: Event-related Conceptual Metaphors with Expressions (Radden and Dirven, 2007)

Conceptual metaphor	Metaphorical expression
Understanding is seeing	I don't see your point.
States are containers	He is in a mess.
Change is motion	The telephone went dead.
Causes are forces	His nagging sent me into a frenzy.

4.3 Event Schema in Cognitive Linguistics

In Cognitive linguistics too, the sentence – the form realizing a message or proposition – is considered to be centered around the event. Events in turn have their conceptual core in Event Schemas (Radden and Dirven, 2007). The definitions in Cognitive linguistics attempt to refer to Event Schema as a mental model, a construal, of an event forming a semantic basis for its linguistic expression.

According to Kendall (2008), a listener – or a reader – of a text is able to construct the gist of the event even when it is not fully assimilated by them, and this is what is meant by event schema. When speakers confront an event in real world it is complex in content, so to express them they pick out only what is salient to the situation with a particular topic-focus and perspective (Langacker, 1987; Givón, 2001; Croft and Wood, 2000; Langacker, 2008).

Event schema refers to a structured representation of the event and the components associated with it such as event types and argument roles (Huang et al, 2016). It is the basic configuration of thematic roles such as agent and theme which together constitute an event

(Radden and Dirven, 2007). Events are grouped into a small set of types, known as Event Schemas (Verspoor, Dirven and Radden, 2004).

Fig.1 Event Schema as the Conceptual Core of Event (Radden and Dirven, 2007)

In the above diagram that models the event from a Cognitive linguistic perspective, it can be seen that the relationship between participants form its conceptual core, i.e. the Event Schema. The time schema deals with the aspect or internal temporal constituency, the grounding concerns the tense or relative temporal location, and modality, and the setting is related to the conditions – spatio-temporal and otherwise – within which the event occurs.

Event schemas are intuitively meaningful categories and have their own diagnostics for identification linguistically. These are in the form of questions using the most prototypical verbs. For example, the Occurrence-Processes type event schema can be identified by the question “*What is happening?*”. There are two well-known classifications for Event Schemas, one with a set of seven types, and another with a taxonomy of three categories and further divided into a total of 11 types. These are elaborated in section 6 of this paper.

This study deals with the concept of Event Schema from a Cognitive linguistic perspective. This chapter is devoted to an analytic description of it, forming a premise to studying translation shifts/IA triggered by certain semantic components of events, one of which is the Event Schema.

5. Annotation Method for Tamil Examples

The CT – non-English – examples in this article are annotated using Leipzig Glossing Rules. These are interlinear morpheme-by-morpheme glossing conventions meant to provide information on meanings and grammatical properties of individual words as well as its parts. It helps linguists consistently use glossing notation conventions. Leipzig Glossing Rules provide ten rules and sub-rules within them in such a way that the linguists can be flexible about the degree of details in applying them as suits their purposes. Clearly, its purpose is not to present an analysis in a certain method, but to present relevant information in a structured way for support and easier presentation of the analysis (Max Planck Institute for Evolutionary Anthropology [MPIEA], 2008).

The convention requires to state an example being interlinearly glossed in three rows or lines, with the first row stating the non-English example in italics and the second providing a word-to-word translation with grammatical category notations for the word and the morphemes

within them as appropriate for the purposes of the material being written. The words in the first and the second rows are vertically aligned with wider inter-word spaces to accommodate such alignment. In the third row, a paraphrased English version of the sentence is provided with regular interword spaces and without vertical alignment with the above rows (MPIEA, 2008).

In this study, the grammatical information of a word considered default in the text is not generally glossed if not required to be stated explicitly, to limit the line length and avoid overflow of the gloss to a next line. For example, the singular (SG) noun is not stated and the nominative case (NOM) for an initial noun – generally a Subject – is not stated, unless otherwise required to be labeled explicitly.

The notations to represent morphosyntactic categories are provided in small caps. The Verbs are labeled for the tense and PNG suffix as available besides any auxiliaries or clitics. The pronouns and the nouns – including named entities – are labeled for case, and the nouns are provided number labels too, both as required. Also, where needed, labeling is provided to designate adjectives, adverbs, pronoun types and even determiners.

6. Definition and Classification

Event schema (pl. Event Schemata or Schemas) is related to how the event is construed with respect to the role of its participants. It is determined by configuration of such roles and shed light on the flow of energy between them or its absence. Participant roles refer to a subset of thematic roles that participate in a **conceptual core** (Radden and Dirven, 2007). Others are non-participant roles, as those realized in adverbials or SETTINGS. A conceptual core is a relation formed with a combination of two or more conceptual entities participating in it, as shown in the examples below.

(1a) Thar is a desert in Rajasthan. [theme – theme/essive]

(1b) Divya painted the wall. [agent – theme]

(2a) *iTli enakku mikavum piTikkum.* [experiencer – cause]

idly-ACC I-DAT very-much like-FUT

I like idly very much.

(2b) *andtat tuNi mirutuvaaka irundtatu.* [theme – theme/essive]

that cloth soft-ADV be-PST.3SGN

The cloth was soft.

In the example (1a) above, for example, participant roles are theme and theme, while the locative is a non-participant role. The event schema is determined by the role configuration between theme and theme in (1a), agent and theme in (1b), experiencer and cause in 2(a), and theme and theme in (2b). Their respective event schema are “being”, “doing”, “experiencing” and “being”, as will be seen later under subsection 4.4 on Classification in this chapter.

Two approaches for the classification of event schemas have been recently proposed from the Cognitive perspective. Irrespective of the classification approaches, the main issues associated with each Event Schemas are the relationship between the participant roles, the realizing sentence pattern(s) and predicate constructions along with their alternants if any they tend to take, the flow of energy – or its absence – and its direction and intensity, and agentivity among others.

This study adopts two well-known classification schemes of event schemata from the Cognitive perspective, one in Verspoor, Dirven and Radden (2004) and the other in Radden and Dirven (2007), with the latter as the premise. The former presents seven types which are indicated by questions of prototype Verbs. The latter presents eleven types and is subsumed under three “worlds of experience” and further subdivisions.

6.1 Grouping 1: Seven Types

The classification of Event Schema in Verspoor, Dirven and Radden (2004) is a list of the following seven types: “Being” Schema, “Happening” Schema, “Doing” Schema, “Experiencing” Schema, “Having” Schema, “Moving” Schema, and “Transferring” Schema. These designations derive from the prototypical Verbs that ask about events. For example, “what is happening?” is answered by the “Happening” Schema. These prototypical Verbs are *be*, *happen*, *do*, *move*, *have*, *see*, *feel*, etc.

Table-1: Configuration of "roles" in Event Schemas

	Schema Label	Participants			
		First	Second	Third	
1	“Being”	Patient	Essive		Who or what is some entity (like)?
2	“Happening”	Patient	(Patient)		What is happening?
3	“Doing”	Agent	(Patient)		What is someone doing?
4	“Experiencing”	Experiencer	Patient		What does someone feel, see, etc.?
5	“Having”	Possessor	Patient		What does an entity have?
6	“Moving”	(Agent)	Patient	Goal	Where is an entity moving?
7	“Transferring”	Agent	Receiver	Patient	To whom is an entity transferred?

These event schemas could take one, two or three participant roles, whose set consists of Agent, Patient, Goal, Receiver, Essive, Experiencer, and Possessor. Some of the schemas are purely non-agentive, some only agentive, and others could be either. Agentivity is an ontological feature of an event, whereby the actualization of the event is effected by an agent, usually animate human. The **agent** could be non-human animate being as well and sometimes the human

language is expressed in such a way that even an inanimate entity is construed as **agent** (Declerck, 2006).

A closely related notion is the flow of energy in events. The participant role of **agent** is the source of energy, out of which it flows, while the **patient** and **experiencer** roles typically undergo energy. The “being” schema does not involve energy flow, as is the “having” schema despite the occurrence of **patient**. The energy flow thus has its direction as well intensity which will be dealt with in detail in the sections 7 to 9, where these seven types will also be mapped to the twelve-type taxonomy incorporating relevant issues from this classification method.

6.2 Grouping 2: Eleven Types

The second classification is more systematic – a taxonomy – and offered in Radden and Dirven (2007). The present study adopts this as the premise for a detailed treatment of the event schema types with examples, while also incorporating relevant points of description from the Grouping I. The framework used to organize the list of event schemas in this taxonomy are the three “worlds of experience” of a language user, namely **material**, **psychological** and **force-dynamic**. Hence, these are descriptive/cognitive linguistic categories and have overlaps without very clear-cut boundaries.

The Material world is a structured world of entities with their dynamics of existence, change and processes and includes not only non-human participants but also non-active or non-agentive humans. They are further divided into subgroups of Occurrence, Spatial and Possession. The Occurrence subgroup includes both states and processes; the latter subdivided into transition and steady state. The Spatial subgroup includes location and motion schemas, the latter being non-agentive. All the schemas within all the subgroups commonly involve the role of **theme**. This is nearly the same as the role **patient** in the Grouping I but also covers the **essive**.

Table-2: A taxonomy for canonical event schemas and its mapping with Grouping I

S. No.	World of Experience	Schema type/subtype	Roles	Grouping I type
1	Material world	Occurrence/states	T — (T)	being
2		Occurrence/processes	T — (T)	happening
3		Spatial/location	T — L	being
4		Spatial/motion	T — G	moving
5	Psychological world	Possession	P — T	having
6		Emotion	E — C	experiencing
7		Perception/Cognition	E — T	experiencing
8	Force-Dynamic	Action	A — T	doing
9		Self-motion	A — G	moving
10		Caused-motion	A — T — G	moving
11		Transfer	A — R — T	transferring

The Psychological world refers to people’s internal world mentally experienced (extra-linguistic sense) and conceptualized by sentient humans. It consists of sensations, emotions, perceptions and thoughts. The schemas under this division commonly have the role **experiencer**. They are of two subgroups/types, one with high external stimulus and low experiencer’s control and is termed as emotional schema; and the other with low external stimulus and medium to high experiencer’s control and is termed as perception/cognition schema.

Force-dynamic world is an external world of action, force, and cause and effects. Its schemas are goal-directed actions mostly of human agents but also of other causal entities as instigators of events, with the agent being the energy source. They are action, self-motion, caused-motion, and transfer schemas.

The set of participant roles used in this taxonomy is somewhat different from that of Grouping I and consists of Agent, Theme, Location, Goal, Possessor, Experiencer, Cause and Receiver. While most of the roles are same in both, the **patient** in Grouping I is replaced by **theme** in this taxonomy, with minor differences that will be detailed under the respective categorial descriptions. Similarly, **cause** is a role that does not figure in Grouping I. A comparison of Tables 1 and 2 would help identify the divergence more easily and clearly.

7. Material World Event Schemas

We have already noted that “**theme**” is the common participant role across the schemas under the “material world of experience”. These schemas are grouped into three subtypes of Occurrence, Spatial and Possession. They are all non-agentive.

7.1 Occurrence Schemas

These refer to the way things are or happen and consist of States and Processes. It is important to note that these designations, though the same in nomenclature as that used for Aktionsart types, have different denotations. They refer to event schemas here, while internal temporal constituency types under Aktionsart.

States do not involve any flow of energy, and are realized by copular construction in CE and CT. This sentence pattern serves as the formal device to express any relation between participant roles, such as, for example, similarity or dissimilarity. Both the roles are **themes**. However, in Grouping I, the second is termed **essive**. States cover one subgroup of “being” schema and include those that convey identifier, class membership and attribution.

(3a) She is my cousin. [Identifier]

(3b) Thar is a desert in Rajasthan. [Class membership]

(3c) The cloth was silky and smooth. [Attribution]

(4a) *avarkaL engkaL aasiriyarkaL*. [Identifier]

they our-EXCL teacher-PL

They are our teachers.

(4b) *penkuyin oru turuvap piraandtiya paRavai.* [Class membership]
 penguin one polar region-ADJ bird
 Penguin is a polar region bird.

(4c) *avaLukku tan sakootaranai viTa oru vayatu kuRaivu.* [Attribution]
 she-DAT her-REFL brother-ACC than one age less
 She is a year younger than her brother.

It can be noted from the examples above, that the copular construction in CT for this event schema tends to take verbless/nominal sentences, especially when the temporal location denoted is in the present time zone.

Processes map on to as the “happening” event schema in Grouping I. The first participant role, **theme**, undergoes/subject to energy. The second participant role, which is also **theme**, does not necessarily occur for all events, hence marked within parentheses to indicate its optionality in Table Y. Though the Processes are obviously non-agentive, the **theme** has a degree of autonomy – in a varying scale – with respect to the Process, as will be shown in the examples. Processes are of two types, Transition and Steady Process

Transitions are event schema that refers to a change of state. This, of course, could be abrupt or gradual, controlled or uncontrolled, and expected or otherwise. The realizing sentence pattern uses transition Verbs, especially Inchoative Verbs, and/or other devices that signal change of state both in CE and CT.

- (5a) The jar broke. [abrupt]
 (5b) You never grow old. [gradual]
 (5c) Beverly fell in love. [uncontrolled]
 (5d) Your application has been processed. [expected]

(6a) *kal uruNdu vizundtatu.* [uncontrolled]
 stone roll-INF fell-PST.3SGN
 The stone rolled down.

(6b) *seyti kaaTTuttii pool paraviyatu.* [gradual]
 news wild-fire like spread-PST.3SGN
 The news went viral.

(6c) *ndamatu kanavu ndanavaakiviTTatu.* [expected]
 our-INCL dream realize-INTR.PST.COMPL.3SGN
 Our dream has come true.

- (6d) *pookkuvarattu viLakku sivappaaka maaRiyatu.* [abrupt]
 traffic light red-ADV change-PST.3SGN
 The traffic light turned red.

Steady Process refers to an event schema that denotes on-going “happening” and does not signal a change of state. However, they could be bounded, with an endpoint that is implicit or explicitly mentioned. Those without such a signification are unbounded. There is a special type of Steady Processes, that could be bounded or unbounded, and concerned typically with weather conditions and the like, and are known as Meteorological Processes.

The sentence patterns used are/ have intransitive constructions and extraposition construction copulatives, especially for meteorological processes. However, CT does not have extraposition constructions.

- (7a) Her kid was crying. [unbounded]
 (7b) The drunk sailor staggered down the road. [bounded]

- (8a) *ndeeRRu visaaraNai ndaTaipeRRatu.* [bounded]
 yesterday enquiry happen-PST.3SGN
 There was an enquiry yesterday.

- (8b) *engkaL taattaavukku muussu vaangkukiRatu.* [unbounded]
 our-EXCL grandfather-DAT breathe-hard-PRS.3SGN
 Our grandfather is panting.

Meteorological Processes

- (9a) It has been raining every day last week.
 (9b) The weather is clearing up now.

- (10a) *ndeeRRu peeykkaaRRu viisiyatu.*
 yesterday furious-wind blow-PST.3SGN
 A furious wind blew yesterday.

- (10b) *inRu veyil koLuttukiratu.*
 today heat burn-INTR.PRS.3SGN
 It's damn hot today.

7.2 Spatial Schemas

The participant roles whose relation is indicated in the Spatial Schemas are **theme** and **location** or **trajectory/goal**. They are of course non-agentive, and subdivided into static and dynamic variants, respectively known as Location and Motion Schemas.

The **Location schema** is one type of “being” schema in Grouping I, those that express location or indicate existentiality, or both. The location could be neutral or specific. There is no energy involved in this event schema. The sentence pattern takes copulative construction in both CE and CT. For the ‘existential’, CE tends to use extraposition construction, which as already does not occur at all in CT.

(11a) Cape of Good Hope is in South Africa. [Location]

(11b) There is an important issue to address. [Existential]

(12a) *kanniyaakumari indtiyaavin tenkooTiyil amainduLLatu.* [Location]

Kanyakumari India-GEN southern-tip-LOC locate-INTR.PRS.PRF.3SGN

Kanyakumari is located at the southern tip of India.

(12b) *ingkee pala kalluurikaL irukkinRana.* [Location+Existential]

here many college-PL be-PRS.3PLN

There are many colleges here.

The **Motion schema** is the dynamic variant of the Spatial type of schemas. It corresponds to one type of “moving” schema in Grouping I that is non-agentive. It involves flow of energy along a trajectory, having its image schema as Source-Path-Goal. The entity that “moves” takes **theme** as the participant role. The description of trajectory could be complete with the occurrence of all the roles – Source-Path-Goal – or partial, with only one or two of them. However, the most salient of them tends to be the **goal**, which is also a participant role in the event schema, the other two being non-participant roles.

The Motion schema not only includes physical/material motion but also events with temporal and metaphorical meanings connoting a trajectory. Further, its description could combine the movement and manner in a single Verb or split them, the former is known as conflation and the latter as separation. The Motion schema is mostly bounded, with exceptions such as the planetary motion.

The sentence pattern that the Motion schema takes uses intransitive Verbs with conflation or separation structure. CE sentences occur more frequently in the conflation pattern than CT, an important asymmetry (IA) to be studied.

(13a) This train goes to Shamli. [goal]

(13b) The ball fell from the terrace into the well. [source-goal]

(13c) The marathon went from the stadium to the beach via the connecting road. [source-path-goal]

(13d) The moon revolves around the earth. [unbounded]

(13e) The Roman empire lasted from 753 BC to 476 AD. [conflation/temporal]

(13f) The Mughals rose in 1526 and fell in 1857. [separation/temporal]

(14a) *kaaviri talaikkaaveeriyil uruveTuttu irutiyaaka vangak kaTalil kalakkiratu.*
 Kaveri Talakaveri-LOC originate-INF finally Bay-of-Bengal-LOC join-PST.3SGN
 Kaveri originates in Talakaveri and culminates in the Bay of Bengal. [source-goal]

(14b) *peerundtu sitamparattilirundtu putusseeri vaziyaaka sennaikku senRatu.*
 bus Chidambaram-ABL Puducherry via-ADV Chennai-DAT go-PST.3SGN
 The bus went to Chennai from Chidambaram via Puducherry. [source-path-goal]

(14c) *un vaazkkai eppaTip pookiratu?* [metaphorical/path]
 your life how go-PRS.3SGN
 How is your life going?

(14d) *viLaiyaaTTaaka toTangkiya peessu vivaatamaaka muTindtatu.* [metaphorical]
 play-COMP start-PTCP talk argument-COMP end-PST.3SGN
 The conversation that started as fun ended in an argument.

(14e) *ndikazssi kaalai pattu mutal maalai aindtu varai naTaipeRum.*
 event morning ten from evening five until happen-FUT.3N
 The event will be held from 10 am to 5 pm. [conflation/temporal]

(14f) *indtap pooTTi eTTu maNikku toTangki pattarai maNikku muTiyum.*
 this competition eight hours-DAT begin-INF half-past-ten hours-DAT finish-FUT.3N
 This competition will begin at eight o'clock and finish at ten o'clock. [separation/temporal]

7.3 Possession Schema

It is the same as “having” event schema in Grouping I, and relates the roles of **possessor** and **theme**. The possession could be material, mental or abstract, or could be denoting relationship of affected-affection, whole-part, and kinship/social relation. In another perspective, they are grouped as alienable and inalienable possession. The former occurs where the possessed can be separated from the possessor, while in the latter they have an inseparable link.

The Possession schema has both dynamic and static construals, with the former using “have” construction and the latter occurring with “be”/copulative construction. Alienable possession can occur as both in CE, while inalienable possession is restricted to the “have” construction only. CT tends to differ considerably in this regard, where largely the possession schema is expressed with static construal using copulative, and only very infrequently with the dynamic, mostly with alienable possession, especially the material type. This can be observed from the CT examples below.

Radden and Dirven (2007) has noted that some other languages too – e.g. Russian, Finnish and Japanese – exhibit this phenomenon, and clearly sees a conceptual affinity between

the location construal in “*be*”/copulative construction and the possession construal in “*have*” construction.

(15a) David has a beautiful garden. [material]

(15b) She has a wonderful smile. [abstract]

(15c) Javid had a backache last week. [affected]

(15d) We have a cousin too. [kinship]

(15e) The complex houses a clock tower. [part-whole]

(15f) There is a clock tower within the complex [static construal]

(15g) The bungalow is his. [static construal]

(16a) *ndaan ainduuRu ruupaay vaittirukkiReen.* [dynamic construal]

I five rupee have-PRS.1SG

I have five rupees.

(16b) *enniTam oru ruupaay kuuTa illai.* [material]

I-LOC one rupee even be-NEG

I don't have even a rupee.

(16c) *avaLukku eeraaLamaana kanavukaL uLLana.* [abstract]

she-DAT lot dream-PL be-PRS.3PLN

She has a lot of dreams.

(16d) *poona varuTam en talayil ndiRaiya poTuku irundtatu.* [affected]

last year my head-LOC lot dandruff be-PRS.3SGN

Last year I had a lot of dandruff in my hair.

(16e) *andta aRaiyil oru katavum iraNTu jannalkaLum uLLana.* [part-whole]

that room-LOC one door-COM two window-PL.COM be-PRS.3PLN

The room has a door and two windows.

(16f) *engaLukku iraNTu piLLaikal.* [kinship]

we-EXCL.DAT two kid-PL

We have two kids.

(16g) *enakku iraNTu akkaamaarkaL irukkiRaarkaL.* [kinship]

I-DAT two elder-sister-PL be-PRS.3PL

I have two elder sisters.

8. Psychological World Event Schemas

These schemas correspond to the “experiencing” schema in Grouping I, and are non-agentive too. They are grouped into two types: Emotion schema and Perception/Cognition schema. The participant role **experiencer** is common to both the types that undergoes energy, being affected by an external stimulus from the **cause** (emotion) or **theme** (cognition/perception).

The external stimulus, which is the other participant in the event, could be a concrete object, abstract object or another event. The sentence pattern could take constructions with **experiencer** as the primary participant or vice versa, within the limits of availability of expressions in the language. Further, the construal could be dynamic or static, resulting respectively in a transitive, intransitive or copulative construction. CE frequently uses dynamic construals, with the static alternant possible for many cases. CT, on the other hand, tends to use static construals largely for this schema with exceptions. These are shown in CT examples below.

8.1 Emotion Schema

Emotion schema is generally triggered by high external stimulus and the **experiencer** has a low control over the evoked response. The **experiencer** could be implicit too, especially when the speaker – in first person – is the **experiencer**.

(17a) His new car looked awesome. [implicit experiencer]

(17b) The people were enraged at the price hike. [experiencer-primary]

(17c) I felt disappointed with his reply. [experiencer-primary]

(17d) His reply disappointed me. [experiencer-secondary]

(18a) *un pazakkavazakkangkal aruvaruppaaka irukkiratu.* [implicit experiencer]
 your habit-PL disgust-ADV be-PRS.3SGN
 Your habits are disgusting.

(18b) *tiraippaTa isai enakku mikavum piTikkum.* [experiencer-passive]
 film music I-DAT very-much like-FUT.3N
 I like film music very much.

(18c) *jananikku ndaaykalaik kaNTaal payam.* [experiencer-passive]
 Janani-DAT dogs-ACC see-COND fear
 Janani is scared of dogs.

(18d) *kairali avarai virumpukiRaaL.* [experiencer-active]
 Kairali he-ACC love-PRS.3SGF
 Kairali loves him.

Further variations of construals as states and processes and their predicate constructions are shown in the following examples. CT sentences do not occur in extraposition construction.

(19a) I'm amazed at George's stupidity. [stative passive]

(19b) George's stupidity amazes me. [emotional process]

(19c) George's stupidity is amazing. [emotional state]

(19d) It is amazing how stupid George is. [extraposition]

(20a) *andtak kaTTiTattai kaaNumpootu piramippaaka irukkiratu.* [stative passive]

that building-ACC see-DUR amaze-ADV be-PRS.3SGN

It is amazing to see that building.

(20b) *andtak kaTTiTam ennai piramikka vaikkiratu.* [emotional process]

that building I-ACC amaze-INF make-PRS.3SGN

That building makes me amazed.

(20c) *andtak kaTTitam piramikkattakkatu.* [emotional state]

that building amaze-PTCP.NMLZ

That building is amazing.

Table-3: Control/Stimulus in World of Psychology Events

	experiencer's control	external stimulus
emotion	low	high
perception	medium	low
cognition	high	low

8.2 Perception/Cognition Schema

The non-emotion type of the “experiencing” schema is Perception/Cognition schema. Here, the external stimulus is low, while the experiencer's control is medium (perception) to high (cognition). The same Verb could denote percept or concept (cognition) depending upon whether they **assume** a physical or metaphorical sense.

(21a) I distinctly heard the saxophone. [perception]

(21b) I vividly remember the main melody. [cognition]

(21c) She thinks he is wasting her precious time. [cognition]

(22a) I see the mountains. [percept]

(22b) I see it's raining. [percept or concept]

(22c) I see your point. [concept]

- (23a) *angkee oru pulveLiyai avarkaL kaNTaarkaL.*
 there one grassland-ACC they see-PST.3PL
 They beheld a grassland there.
- (23b) *varukiRa vaziyil oru vinootamaana saptam keeTTatu.*
 come-INF.PRS way-LOC one strange sound hear-PST.PAS.3SGN
 A strange sound was heard enroute.
- (23c) *avarkaL jeyikka maaTTaarkaL enRu enakku teriyum.*
 they win-FUT.NEG.3PL that-QUOT I-DAT know-FUT.3SGN
 I knew they would not win.
- (23d) *enakku Tellikkup pooka tikkeT veeNTum.*
 I-DAT Delhi-DAT go-INF ticket want
 I want a ticket to Delhi.
- (24a) *indta malaiyilirundtu uuree terikiratu. [percept]*
 this hill-ABL town-EMP seen-PRS.3SGN
 The entire town is seen from this hill.
- (24b) *rayil varuvatu poolat terikiratu. [percept or concept]*
 train come-NMLZ seem-PRS.3SGN
 The train seems to be coming.
- (24c) *avanukku pala mozikaL teriyum. [concept]*
 he-DAT many language-PL know-FUT.3SGN
 He knows multiple languages.

9. Force-Dynamics World Schemas

The event schemas in the force-dynamics world of experience are all agentive as noted earlier. The agents are typically sentient human or non-human animate beings, while it could also be agent-like causes and enabling conditions. These schemas involve high flow/intensity of energy, and explicate cause and effect (provide c&e imagery) of events.

9.1 Action Schema

The action schema corresponds to the “doing” schema in Grouping I. Typically their sentence pattern takes transitive constructions. In CE, an alternant Middle construction frequently occurs with enabling-condition ‘agents’.

The **agent** is the source of energy directed towards a target, the **theme**, where the energy is ‘absorbed’. Radden and Dirven (2007) formulates this as an ‘energy chain’, viewed from different vantage points (of participant roles) and mentions in this regard the **instrument** as an intermediate stage in the transfer of energy between the **agent** and **theme**. The **theme** realization may range from no object through optional object to affected or effected object.

Fig. 1 Energy Chain Illustration (Radden and Dirven, 2007)

Further, this event schema also entails degrees of different qualities such as the degree of energetic action, the degree of transitivity, the degree of affectedness of theme, and the degree of force of energy source.

(25a) They were jogging together. [no object]

(25b) She was cooking all day yesterday. [object optional]

(25c) Divya painted the wall. [object-affected]

(25d) He was drawing a train on the blackboard. [object-effected]

(25e) He put water on the blackboard. [object-affected]

(26a) *avar eppootum kattikkoNTee iruppaar.* [no object]

he always shout be-FUT.3SG

He keeps shouting.

(26b) *en ndaNpan muukkuppiTikka saappiTTaan.* [object optional]

my friend stuff-ADV eat-PST.3SGM

My friend ate like a glutton.

(26c) *avaL vaasalukku taNNiir teLittaaL.* [object-affected]

she entrance-DAT water sprinkle-PST.3SGM

She sprinkled water around the entrance.

(26d) *ndaan taRseyalaaka jaaTiyai uTaittuviITTeen.* [object-affected]

I-DAT accident-ADV jar-ACC break-PST.COMPL.1SG

I broke the jar accidentally.

(26e) *maitreyi kaTTurai ezutukiRaaL*. [object-effected]

Maitreyi essay-ACC write-PRS.PROG.3SGF

Maitreyi is writing an essay.

9.2 Self-motion Schema

The Self-motion schema is almost the same as the Motion schema under “Material world” events, except that it is agentive. The impacted participant in this schema is the ‘self’ and it is implicit. The sentence pattern, therefore, it tends to take is of intransitive construction. This schema is a type of the “moving” schema in Grouping I, and can be expressed in terms of a combination as “doing+ moving”.

(27a) We drove 200 miles from Salem to Ernakulam. [spatial]

(27b) The kids walked to the school. [spatial]

(27c) That millionaire grew from rags to riches. [metaphorical]

(28a) *ndaan ndaaLaikku uurukkup pookiReen*. [spatial]

I tomorrow-DAT hometown-DAT go-FUT.1SG

I am going to my hometown tomorrow.

(28b) *andtas siruvarkaL kaalai mutal maalai varai viLaiyaaTuvar*. [temporal]

that kid-PL morning from evening till play-FUT.3PL

Those kids play from morning to evening.

(28c) *anniyaraaka irundta avaL tooziyaaka maaRinaaL*. [metaphorical]

stranger-COMP be-PST.INF she friend-COMP change-FUT.3SGF

From being a stranger, she became a friend.

9.3 Caused-motion Schema

The Caused-motion schema is also almost the same as the Motion schema under “Material world” events, except that it is agentive. The impacted participant in this schema, the **theme**, is another entity explicitly mentioned. The sentence pattern it tends to take is of transitive construction. This schema is a type of the “moving” schema in Grouping I, and can as well be expressed in terms of a combination as “doing+ moving”.

(29a) He kicked the ball into the net. [spatial]

(29b) Santa Claus puts sweets into the stockings. [spatial]

(29c) The alchemist turned the metal into gold. [metaphorical]

(29d) The police searched the house from noon till midnight. [temporal]

- (30a) *vivasaayikal vaikkoolai laariyil eeRRinar.* [spatial]
farmer-PL hay-ACC truck-LOC load-PST.3PL
The farmers loaded hay onto the truck.
- (30b) *avan tan kuTumpattaarai sinimaavukku azaittus senRaan.* [spatial]
he his-REFL family-ACC movie-DAT take-PST.3SGM
He took his family to a movie.
- (30c) *tiruTarkaL atikaalai varai andta vangkiyil koLLaiyaTittanar.* [temporal]
robber-PL early-hours until that bank-LOC loot-PST.3PL
The robbers looted the bank until early hours.
- (30d) *ndaangkaL kaLimaNNai pommaikalaaka maaRRinoom.* [metaphorical]
we-EXCL clay-ACC doll-PL.COMP convert-PST.1PL
We converted the clay into dolls.

9.4 Transfer Schema

This schema corresponds to the “transferring” schema in Grouping I. and incorporates the “moving/motion” schemas, the “doing/action” schema and the “having/possession” schema. An entity, the **theme**, is ‘moved’ from the ‘possession’ of one to another by the **agent**. This schema too can denote either physical or abstract/metaphorical transfer. Clearly the transfer schema is agentive and involves flow of energy from a first ‘possessor’ to a second.

CE takes ditransitive or caused motion construction to denote transfer event schema, while CT sentences for this do not have a ditransitive construction and only occur in the latter pattern. Further Radden and Dirven (2007) has pointed out certain nuances and limitations in the use of both these constructions in CE. In the caused motion construction patterns, while the *to*-phrase forms a part of the conceptual core, the *for*-phrase does not, where the former denotes the recipient-**goal** and the latter the beneficiary-**goal**. However, in the ditransitive construction this distinction is not conveyed. In addition, when the beneficiary-**goal** is meant, the non-creative actions do not seem to sit well with the ditransitive constructions among English users (Allerton, 1978).

- (31a) Could you cook me a meal? [creative action]
(31b) *Could you taste me this wine? [non-creative action]

Examples

- (32a) Margaret gave her son a rare collection of books. [physical]
(32b) The boss presented his proposal to his colleagues. [abstract]
(32c) Asha offered the shoppers a discount. [abstract]
(32d) Asha offered a discount for the shoppers. [beneficiary-goal]

- (32e) Anne passed on the message to her friend. [recipient-goal]
 (32f) He gave me an idea. [metaphorical]
 (32g) He gave us a speech. [metaphorical]
- (33a) *tangkam avaLukku anpaLippuk koTuttaal*. [physical]
 Thangam she-DAT gift give-PST.3SGF
 Thangam gave her a gift.
- (33b) *massaan ndamakku kaTitam anuppiyuLLaar*. [physical]
 brother-in-law we-INCL.DAT letter send-PRS.PRF.3SG
 Our brother-in-law has sent us a letter.
- (33c) *andtap peeraasiriyar engkaLukku moziyiyal kaRRut tandtaar*. [abstract]
 that professor we-EXCL.DAT linguistics teach-PST.3SG
 That professor taught us linguistics.
- (33d) *peeraRivaaLan tan manaivikku anaittaiyum vazangkinaan*. [physical/abstract]
 Perarivaalan her-REFL wife-DAT everything-ACC offer-PST.3SGM
 Perarivaalan offered her wife everything.
- (33e) *paaTTi engkaLukku katai sonnaar*. [metaphorical]
 grandma we-EXCL.DAT story-ACC tell-PST.3SGF
 Grandma told us a story.
- (33f) *aasiriyar maaNavarkaLukku aRivurai nalkinaar*. [metaphorical]
 teacher student-PL.DAT advice-ACC offer-PST.3SG
 The teacher offered the students advice.
- (33g) *anta atikaariyai miinvaLat tuRaikku maaRRiviTTaarkaL*. [metaphorical]
 that officer-ACC fisheries department-DAT change-TR.PST.COMPL.3PL
 That officer was transferred to the Fisheries department.

10. Conclusion

The sections above are a very brief description of the event schema, a semantic component of events represented by Verbs that is of non-temporal dimension. It relates to how an event is posed or construed with respect to its chief arguments known as participant roles. This in turn determines the constructional form of a sentence consisting of the event. The constructional forms are not always symmetric across languages – CE and CT in this study – for a given event schema. This gives rise to Interlingual Asymmetry, or a translation shift when mediating text from source language to target language, here CE and CT respectively. It is due to

this relevance to the purposes of the larger study that the event schema was taken for a comprehensive treatment here.

The framework used for the classification and description of different event schemas was from a Cognitive Linguistic perspective, drawn largely from Radden and Dirven (2007) as well as Verspoor, Dirven and Radden (2004). An eleven-type grouping from the former reference was adopted to present the event schema types systematically, broadly divided as the schemas of Material World, Psychological World and Force-Dynamic World. Further subdivisions of these are shown in table 2.

Each type is also mapped with the seven-type grouping given in Verspoor, Dirven and Radden (2004) to show the correspondence between the two classification methods that follow the Cognitive Linguistic approach to studying events. More importantly, each event schema was elucidated listing various denotations – or communicative functions – that it can serve, and with sufficient examples in both CE and CT.

This paper serves as a premise for a detailed exploration and analysis of translation shift and the concomitant IA carried out in a wider study, where it would be shown how that the static vs dynamic construal of event schemas plays a very significant role in the occurrence of cross-linguistic formal asymmetry in sentential as well as predicate constructions, especially with the changes in syntactic functions or case marking of an event's main arguments.

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